

THE ROLE OF THE SCHOOL SUPERVISOR IN THE PROEB MATHEMATICS ASSESSMENT

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5634942

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The school supervisor is the one who looks after the well-being of his school: students, parents, teachers, school community. It is he who takes initiatives on the changes that must take place in the school, seeking to improve its educational performance.

The school supervisor plays a fundamental role in the external evaluations that are proposed to the school, such as those in the State of Minas Gerais in the area of Mathematics, the Evaluation Program of the Public Basic Education Network (Proeb).

Proeb is an external and census assessment that seeks to diagnose public education in the State of Minas Gerais (Minas Gerais, 2020). Therefore, its application in schools is of paramount importance so that its results contribute to advancing the quality of education.

The objective of this work is to analyze how the school supervisor can help in the performance of Proeb. In addition, it will be understood how this professional can work together with the faculty and students for the success of the assessment, making them represent an extremely important agent in the assessment process.

The methodology used in the article was qualitative research, as "it is not concerned with numerical representation, but with deepening the understanding of a social group, an organization, etc." (Silveira; Córdoba, 2009).

The proposed basis for this article was based on authors Pereira, Pinto and Viana and on documents from Instituto Unibanco, in addition to information from the Proeb website, which supports the idea to be developed in the article.

Theoretical foundation

One of the possibilities for improving the school can be through external evaluations periodically proposed to schools. These assessments seek to assess students in a certain scope, which can be municipal, state, federal and international. In this perception of evaluation, the school supervisor, together with his pedagogical team, must face these evaluations positively, making it a possibility for change in his school in a positive way.

The supervisor takes a very important position in the school environment, being part of the school management, assisting students, teachers and administrators, such as the school principal, and supporting the students' parents. According to Pires (1990, apud Pereira, 2012), we have to

the school supervisor has different qualities. Its main qualities are that it should effectively be able to promote interaction between groups that work at the school, ensure the quality of teaching, collaborate directly with teachers, students and their families, and above all, transform them into instruments able to facilitate changes.

From this perspective, the school supervisor must carefully encourage the school as a whole. This incentive that is given to students directly interferes with their school performance, and can make them succeed or fail at school. Such stimulus can be given through the intermediary of the teacher or the supervisor. Thus, when the contents of Mathematics are approached, there is a need for constant communication between the supervisor and the professor of the Mathematics discipline.

Interest in the subject should be aroused in students, making learning occur naturally and without the traditional "fear". This fear for Mathematics makes it difficult for the student to assimilate the content, making the teacher use methods that facilitate the understanding of Mathematics so that the teaching-learning process is accessible to students.

The school supervisor must support both the teacher and the student so that the school can perform satisfactorily in the external evaluations proposed by the state and federal governments. At the state level, in Minas Gerais, we have the Simave (Mineiro System for Assessment and Equity in Public Education). At the federal level there is the Saeb (Basic Education Assessment System).

The focus of this work will be the role of the school supervisor in the external assessment of Mathematics proposed by the state, which is the Assessment Program of the Public Basic Education Network (Proeb), which is part of the assessments carried out by SIMAVE since 2000; in them have been evaluated, according to the Department of Education (2019),

students from the 5th and 9th grades of elementary school and the 3rd year of high school in the municipal and state schools of Minas Gerais from 2000 to 2003 and then from 2006 to 2014. From 2015 onwards the number increased. of stages evaluated, alternating between the even and odd years: in the even ones, the same stages continued to be evaluated, while in the odd ones, the 7th year of Elementary School and the 1st year of High School were evaluated, in addition to 3rd year of high school.

Proeb must be seen by the school supervisor as a way to see how your school is in relation to other schools in your city and state, reflecting on whether its management is correct or if it should be modified.

In order to monitor the improvement of the quality of education offered in its network, the State of Minas Gerais seeks, through Proeb, to produce diagnoses on the performance of students in the areas of knowledge evaluated, allowing, once any weakness in this process is identified, that intervention actions are carried out (Minas Gerais, 2008).

It is enough for the school supervisor, when checking the performance of his school on Proeb, to take initiatives in his school, so that he always improves the performance of students in the assessment. However, in the case of school failure, the culprits are not always the students, who almost always take responsibility for the poor performance in the tests. Pinto and Viana (2014, p. 2) emphasize that

it began to be realized that the education system could also be responsible for school failure. In this sense, external evaluation can be a support point, an extra element, to rethink and plan pedagogical action and educational management.

It is then noted the importance of the school supervisor in external evaluations, in the existing possibilities for their work to be positive in the success of their school.

The role of the school supervisor in Proeb

Proeb is “an external and census assessment that seeks to diagnose public education in the State of Minas Gerais” (Minas Gerais, 2008). The results of the evaluation make the municipal and state public authorities develop actions related to public policies aimed at Education and improvements in the pedagogical and didactic actions of the schools involved.

As in other activities performed, the school supervisor must be engaged, committed, involved, and not just act as an advisor or consultant (Medina, 1997). In this scenario, these professionals must develop an attitude of collaboration between the institution's students and faculty, so that their work does not harm either party.

The role played by the supervisor in Proeb is understood as a link between the activities performed by the students, together with the role of the teacher in the classroom. Thus, when the supervisor sees their role in this perspective, they have the ability to understand the real situation of students' learning and the quality of work performed by the teacher in the classroom.

When the supervisor interferes, opines and suggests, at any stage of Proeb, it tends to make the result vicious, incorrect and flawed. In addition, the institution is unable to assess, diagnose and correct possible failures and didactic and pedagogical errors present in the school environment. The professional's contribution to the occurrence of this fact makes the school

have a distant reality, without real evaluations of its school project and of its actions performed, and may even hide the good practices developed there.

The teacher's role in evaluating the Proeb is to create educational strategies with meaning for students, valuing the various experiences that demonstrate that the insertion of digital and extracurricular resources, when well planned, with strategy, can help achieve goals of learning (Lévy, 1995).

Possibilities of developing preliminary assessments to Proeb with the Mathematics teacher and the school supervisor

The school supervisor plays the role of interference for the improvement of your school. In the classroom, this interference is made by the teacher, who is the one who teaches his students.

The Mathematics teacher, when faced with the results of external evaluations, does not always recognize them as potential pedagogical tools, not knowing how to use them well (Instituto Unibanco, 2016). Thus, the teacher must study these results in order to know how to approach the content in which there was failure in the classroom.

This failure is sometimes caused by traditional classroom methodologies; according to Oliveira (2016), “traditional methodologies have been ineffective in helping students to learn to think, reflect, autonomously create solutions for practical situations, for the problems they face”.

Games, computerized classes, technical visits, lectures and interdisciplinary work, among other resources, are some alternatives that the teacher can use in his class so that students can perform well in assessments.

The school supervisor and the teacher must recognize the role of stimulators and mediators of the student's knowledge, knowledge and learning, together with the assessment methodology. It is up to the supervisor and the teacher to act as intermediaries between the learning content and the constructive activity for assimilation (Silva; Navarro, 2012).

The decentralization of the teaching-learning process plays a fundamental role in all stages of student learning. This student must play the role of an agent who builds their knowledge, protagonist of their knowledge and of the different stages of assessment, as highlighted by Silveira (2019):

The teaching-learning process that leads to the understanding of the subject (both teacher and student) as an epistemic subject; a being who knows and builds knowledge. (...) The importance of decentralizing the figure of the teacher in student learning is highlighted. The teacher continues with their functions to teach and the student to learn, but it is important that the teacher does not deliver ready-made answers to the student, but rather that they seek the appropriate answers in their daily lives.

The evaluation before the Proeb time is presented as a need to be a constant, daily process with the participation of groups of students (Silveira, 2019). Based on this constant assessment, the student is fully able to get to Proeb and apply all the knowledge acquired in previous assessments and achieve great success in both theoretical and practical results.

Conclusion

Based on what was presented in this article, it is understood that the school supervisor can and should contribute to external assessments of Mathematics in schools. These professionals must offer the stimulus for success to their students and teachers at the school where they work.

Note the importance of the teacher-student relationship and also the teacher-supervisor relationship, as they work together so that the results are satisfactory, demonstrating the success of the teaching-learning process in the school. These results are also positive for the state, showing the competence of the active Education professionals.

The assessments stipulated by Proeb can be considered diagnostic tools for student learning, diagnostics of the efficiency of the teaching methodologies of the teacher and, finally, the work of guidance and pedagogical supervision of the school supervisor.

The results presented in the Proeb evaluations should be used by the education system, aiming at its improvement, improvement and the creation of new methodologies by governments with the purpose of creating new public policies for Education and, finally, for the teachers can develop contextualised, problematized and interdisciplinary classes, thus offering quality education to all students.

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